

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAMME REGARDING UPDATED WEANING FOOD AMONG MOTHER WITH INFANTS IN THIRUBHUVANAI AT PUDUCHERRY

Living in depression is a big tragedy and not speaking about it to another is a double tragedy

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Abstract—The present study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme regarding updated weaning food among mother with infants residing in Thirubuvanai at Puducherry. The study was Pre experimental one group pre test and post test design. A total of 60 participants who met the inclusion criteria were selected from the Thirubuvanai area at Puducherry by using convenience sampling technique. Reveals that among the association of selected demographic variables with the knowledge regarding complementary feeding among mothers it shows that in pre test there is no significant difference between the level of knowledge with the demographic variables such as age, types of family, education, occupation, religion, monthly income, birth order, diet, nature of marriage and mode of feeding at the level of level $p < 0.05$. and the overall $*P < 0.05$ significant, $**p < 0.001$ & $***-P < 0.001$ Highly significant

Index Terms—Weaning food, Complementary feeding, Mothers with infants, Structured teaching programme, Knowledge, Infant nutrition, Malnutrition prevention

I. Introduction

Weaning is defined as the process started when breast milk is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of infants, and therefore, other foods and liquids are needed, along with breast milk. The target range for complementary feeding is generally taken to be 6 to 24 months of age even though breastfeeding may be continued beyond two years. When breast milk is no longer enough to meet the nutritional needs of the infant, complementary foods should be added to the diet of the child. The transition from exclusive breastfeeding to family foods, referred to as complementary feeding, typically covers the period from 6 to 18-24 months of age, which is a very vulnerable period. **NEED FOR THE STUDY At International Level:** A report conducted by the International level WHO 2010, the highest bottle feeding late at 67% delayed introduction of complementary feeds to exclusively breast feed infants in living in poverty carries the risk of compromised nutritional status leading to under nutrition, if the quality & quantity of BM from malnourished mother is inadequate supply to their nutrition supplement. According to WHO criteria, 22.7% of the infants were anemic at 8 months and 18.1% at 12 months.

At National Level: Department Of Indian Paediatric Association: Malnutrition has been responsible directly (or) indirectly for 60% of 10.9 million deaths annually among children under age five, two things of these deaths are often associated with in appropriate feeding practices occurring during first year of life. Weaning food is the important intervention in saving infant lives. **At State Level:** During the clinical exposure at Sri Manakula Vinayagar Medical College and Hospital, the investigator has come across the varied number of cases of pediatrics. On giving care to the infants and with further interactive sessions with the mother with infants, attending the clinic, the investigator has identified the various problems that are faced by the mothers which in turn affects the health of infants. On further interaction with mothers, the investigator has identified the inadequate knowledge is because of not awareness about weaning food, which in turn creates inadequate knowledge.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAMME REGARDING UPDATED WEANING FOOD AMONG MOTHER WITH INFANTS IN THIRUBHUVANAI AT PUDUCHERRY.”

III. OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the knowledge regarding weaning food among mother with infants
2. To find the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on weaning food among mother with infants
3. To find out the association between knowledge of mother regarding weaning food with their selected demographic variables.

IV. HYPOTHESIS

H1 –There was a significant difference between level of knowledge among mothers regarding updated weaning food.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted to assess The Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme Regarding Updated Weaning Food Among mother with Infants. The study design was Pre experimental one group pre test and post test design. A total of 60 participants who met the inclusion criteria were selected by using convenience sampling technique. The researcher first introduced himself to the participants and developed a rapport communication with them. After the selection of samples the data was collected with the prepared tools.

V. DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL

Part I:

It consist of socio demographic data including age, religion, education, occupation, income, birth order, type of family, diet, nature of marriage and mode of feeding.

Part II:

It consist of knowledge items 20 objective type of multiple choice questions with four distractions. Structured questionnaire which was prepared by the researcher. All the question had only correct answer ,each correct response was awarded a single score according to the pre-determined key. And 0 score was awarded to wrong responses and variation. Total possible maximum score for all the item where 20. This tools which was in English was translated to Tamil.

TABLE 1:

Frequency and percentage wise distribution of demographic variables.

The frequency and percentage wise distribution of demographic variables of married women revealed that majority 46.6 % were in the age group of below 20-30 years, 41.6 % of them belong to 30-40 years, 11.6% of them belong to above 40 years.

TABLE 2:

Frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge of pre- test of Complementary feeding among mothers with infants.

reveals that 70% of mothers have Poor level of knowledge, 30% of mothers have average level of knowledge in pre -test on complementary feeding among mothers with infants.

TABLE 3:

Frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge of complementary feeding post- test among mother with infants .

reveals that mothers have 13.33% Poor level of knowledge, 75% of children have Average level of knowledge and 11.67% of them having Excellent knowledge level in post-test on complementary feeding

Table 4:**Mean and standard deviation of paried I.Ortest of pre-test and post-test of complementary feeding among mothers with infants**

reveals that in pre-test mean value was 7.5 with the standard deviation of 3.65 in post-test mean value was 12.833 with the standard deviation of 2.61. The paired T test value is $t=9.2061$. There is a statistical difference between pre-test and post- test.

Table 5:

Association of frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge regarding complementary feeding among mother with infants

Reveals that among the association of selected demographic variables with the knowledge regarding complementary feeding among mothers it shows that in pre test there is no significant difference between the level of knowledge with the demographic variables such as age, types of family, education, occupation, religion, monthly income, birth order, diet, nature of marriage and mode of feeding of level $p<0.05$

VI. DISCUSSION

The study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme regarding updated weaning food among mothers with infants in Thirubuvanai area at Puducherry.

The total number of sample collected were 60, a Pre experimental one group pre test and post test design was conducted to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme regarding updated weaning food. The demographic variable is age, religion, education, occupation, income, birth order, type of family, diet, nature of marriage and mode of feeding.

This study was conducted to associate the knowledge on updated weaning food with selected demographic variables. In pre test level of knowledge was assessed by structured questionnaires after assessment Structured Teaching Programme regarding updated weaning food was provided after that post test conducted by using same tool..

1. The first objectives was to assess the knowledge regarding weaning food among mother with infants.

ALTERN MED REVet al.,(2012), conducted a descriptive study in 7 villages of Narayanganj district, Bangladesh among 242 mothers to assess their knowledge and attitude regarding breastfeeding and weaning food using pretested questionnaires. Although 83.5% mothers knew that colostrum is good for the child, less than 8 % of them gave it as the first food to their babies. Most mothers did not have the correct knowledge about exclusive breastfeeding and the appropriate time for introduction of weaning foods; and only 3% of them knew how to prepare proper complementary foods.

The mean score of knowledge score of the mothers was only 4±1.7 out of 10, indicating the need for nutrition education in this area.

2. The second objective is To find the effectiveness of structured teaching program me on weaning food among mother with infants

Hungler (et.al) 2011 conducted a study in urban slums of Hyderabad revealed that a poor performance of growth during the latter part of infancy is a reflection of improper weaning food and inadequate consumption of supplementary foods. A study on 250 infants was conducted in rural and urban communities near Indore, India. Results showed that 18.4% and 12.8% of six months. This is due to delayed weaning food and diluted cow's or buffalo's milk.

3.To find out the association between knowledge of mother regarding weaning food with their selected demographic variables.

Platt ET.AL., 2009 conducted study on infant feeding practices among 353 Bedovin families in transition from semi-nomadic to settlement conditions in the Negev area of Israel were compared with those of 302 Jewish families from the same area. Rice was the first solid food to be introduced to Bedovin infants, while fruits and vegetables were the first solids introduced to the Jewish infants. Rice was not an important constituent of the diet of Jewish infants. By age six months, 93 percent of the Jewish infants were eating fruits and vegetables, 78 percent meat, 49 percent, 13 percent, 8 percent and 18 percent among the Bedovins. Bedovin infants feeding practices resembled those prevalent among rural population in developing countries.

Reveals that among the association of selected demographic variables with the knowledge regarding complementary feeding among mothers it shows that in pre test there is no significant difference between the level of knowledge with the demographic variables such as age, types of family, education, occupation, religion, monthly income, birth order, diet, nature of marriage and mode of feeding at the level of level $p < 0.05$.

VII. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A quantitative research approach was selected for this study to evaluate the effectiveness of

Structured Teaching Programme regarding updated weaning food among mothers with infants at Thirubuvanai. The researcher obtained formal permission from ethical committee of Sri Manakula Vinayagar Nursing College, Puducherry. The period of data collection was two week. Totally 60 mothers are selected by using convenience sampling technique. The purpose of the study was explained to the mothers. This study was conducted to associate the knowledge on updated weaning food with selected demographic variables. In pre test level of knowledge was assessed by structured questionnaires after assessment Structured Teaching Programme regarding updated weaning food was provided after that post test conducted by using same tool.

VIII. CONCLUSION

SECTION I:

Frequency and percentage distribution of updated weaning food among mother with infants at selected demographic variables.

SECTION II:

Frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge of pre- test of updated weaning food among mother with infants .

SECTION III:

Frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge of post- test among mother with infants in Thirubuvanai

SECTION IV:

Mean and standard deviation of paired „t“test of pre-test and post-test of updated weaning among mother with infants

SECTION V:

Association of frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge on of updated weaning food among mother with infants

IX. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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